

Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

1 Document Revision History

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2023-07-15	3.0	<p>Updated Table 1 based on progress in initiating or achieving expected impacts. Revised the relevance of initial stakeholder groups. Updated information about types of results generated by the project, and risks and barriers (Table 5). Provided more details about the application of Bayesian network models. Clarified the definition of KPI 3.</p>	Björn Alfthan (GRID-Arendal), Artur Palacz (IOPAN)
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2 General Objectives of ECOTIP and its expected results

This document presents the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR). The Plan has been designed and will be continuously updated in order to meet the objectives of ECOTIP which are:

- to map the current biodiversity of Arctic marine ecosystems and its past and present interaction with external drivers (multiple stressors), using traits as a measure of functional diversity;
- to investigate the vulnerability of marine communities (with different trait compositions), functions and ecosystem services to multiple climatic and non-climatic stressors, and to determine their potential for ecosystem tipping points;
- to use the analysis of functional (trait) diversity to predict a) changes in the local production and type of fisheries and b) in carbon sequestration by biological pump under multiple anthropogenic stressors;
- to engage in dialogue and co-creation of alternative governance structures and adaptation strategies for the local and indigenous communities, as well as industries and regulatory authorities;
- to ensure effective exploitation of the project results in international scientific assessments of Arctic biodiversity change and by policy-makers, to ensure dialogue, communication and dissemination to indigenous societies and European citizens, and to provide recommendations for optimising the monitoring of Arctic biodiversity and ecosystem services.

3 Priorities of the EU call to which ECOTIP responds to

ECOTIP addresses the call LC-CLA-07-2019 subtopic b) Changes in Arctic Biodiversity, under the call - H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2019-2020 'Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: climate action in support of the Paris Agreement'.

***b) Changes in Arctic biodiversity (Research and Innovation action):** Actions should identify and analyse major drivers and implications of changing biodiversity in the Arctic, such as the role of invasive species, and how vulnerable land and/or marine ecosystems are with respect to combined human and natural influences. Actions should assess the ecosystems' responses to both external and internal factors and how these responses are impacting on indigenous populations and local communities at socio-economic level. Actions should also identify adaptation strategies in relation to the changes in Arctic ecosystems.*

The PEDR will be enhanced and optimised throughout the duration of the project to maximise the expected impacts as described in the EU Call:

- the implementation of the new integrated EU policy for the Arctic;
- the IPCC assessments and other major regional and global initiatives;
- enhanced engagement of and the interaction with residents from local communities and indigenous societies.
- support the EU Polar (Research) Cluster

In Table 1 we provide a comprehensive overview of the specific targets determined by the ECOTIP Consortium in relation to each of the expected impacts, and list concrete actions in which the project is or plans to contribute to these targets.

Table 1. The Expected Impact of ECOTIP

	Specific target	ECOTIP contribution	
		Initiated and in progress	Implemented
Contribution for the implementation of the new integrated EU policy for the Arctic	Supporting Paris Agreement on <u>climate change</u> research, and developing a <u>climate adaptation strategy</u> for the Arctic region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigating the effects of climate change on biodiversity and related ecosystem services, including the feed-back loops for carbon sequestration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helping to develop adaptation strategies together with the local communities
	Promoting <u>sustainable development</u> and innovation; enhancing economic, social and environmental resilience of societies, promoting blue growth opportunities including safe shipping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing new insights of the effects of increasing economic activities (shipping, mining, oil exploration) on the Arctic ecosystems and their services Investigating the effect of climate change and other stressors on Indigenous livelihoods and for coastal and off-shore business opportunities (blue economy) Integrating Indigenous knowledge into recommendations for management strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributing to regulatory frameworks on sustainable use of marine resources
	<u>Protecting the Arctic marine environment</u> and strengthening the ecosystem resilience, including biodiversity protection, establishment of marine protected areas and pollution control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping of the multiple stressors, including pollution by oil, heavy metals, litter and invasive species, and investigating their effects on biodiversity, ecosystem functions and their services Helping to optimise monitoring programs as components of the Pan-Arctic Observation System 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing advice and participating in policy dialogues on the priorities for biodiversity and environmental protection

	Specific target	ECOTIP contribution	
	<u>Advancing international collaboration</u> on ocean governance, climate change, maritime environment and safety, fisheries, and research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increasing scientific knowledge about the Arctic Ocean, including observations based on remote sensing ● Engaging in the international research activities in the Arctic through research clusters and science fora 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing new ecosystem data to supporting the international conventions and organisations
	Promoting open data, open infrastructure and contributing to existing observing network efforts, engaging in capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supporting open data and open access policy ● Educating graduate, post-graduate and PhD students and therefore providing for the next generation of Arctic experts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promoting the use of internationally-agreed standards, protocols and best practices produced by relevant SCOR working groups and other made available via Ocean Best Practices initiative ● Disseminating information about ECOTIP's metadata using free and open-source infrastructure (GeoNetwork) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Establishing synergies between ECOTIP's metadata & data GeoNetwork catalogue and similar facilities supporting CAFF and other expert working groups
Contribution to the major regional and global scientific assessments	Intergovernmental science-policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) and other assessments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Contribute with data and models to the future regional biodiversity assessments in the Arctic region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engage in dialogue of policy-relevant tools and methods for biodiversity monitoring, including identification of new indexes
	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enable existing Earth System Models to better resolve ocean biological processes and their role in climate regulation through delivery of new process understanding and a trait-based model approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support improved representation of pelagic ecosystems in the IPCC Reasons for Concern (RFC) framework

	Specific target	ECOTIP contribution	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify priorities and roadmaps for developing data products needed to advance modelling of carbon sequestration and the biological carbon pump in the Arctic 	
	Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON); Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Program (CBMP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect and make available new data for essential biodiversity variables (EBVs) and essential ocean variables (EOVs) according to the requirements for their measurement set jointly by MBON and GOOS Engage in the dialogue for the development of marine EBVs in Arctic, including addressing of the key knowledge-gaps, optimization of monitoring and identification of trait-based indexes representing functional diversity and key ecosystem services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance CBMP's data management by integrating information about ECOTIP's results with the Arctic Biodiversity Data Service
	Arctic Biodiversity Assessment (Arctic Council) Working groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address knowledge-gaps identified in the most recent Arctic biodiversity assessments, particularly on invasive species using eDNA methods and microbial and plankton diversity, and benthic processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide new knowledge on the impact of climate change and other stressors on marine biodiversity in line with the "Climate change impacts on Arctic ecosystems and associated climate feedbacks" planned report Provide recommendations for enhanced and optimised Arctic monitoring
	ICES Working Group on Integrated Ecosystem Assessment in the Greenland Sea; International Arctic Science Committee Marine Working Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide new marine biodiversity, climate and environmental stressor data and provide holistic interpretation of observed changes across the trophic elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide recommendations for enhanced and optimised monitoring in the East Greenland Ecoregion

	Specific target	ECOTIP contribution	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to the science advisory process by engaging in respective working groups proceedings 	
Engagement and interaction with local communities and Indigenous societies	Strategies and initiatives to increase the involvement of Arctic Indigenous peoples in science and engagement of their knowledge systems by the Arctic Council, Greenland Government, and local communities themselves, including adaptation strategy for incorporation of potential changes in fishing resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organise a stake-holder workshop for local communities at the beginning of the project to inform about the project, to ensure <i>active and needs-based engagement</i> of decision makers from the start (including use of Indigenous knowledge to guide study design), and identify early on the social actors and institutions that generate adaptation actions Conduct a series of interviews with local communities during the project to map significant changes in the (human) communities related to changes in past and present fisheries (subsistence as well as commercial), in consultation with the association of fishers and hunters in Greenland (KNAPK) Share and co-produce knowledge to obtain possible scenarios for future changes and alternative paths for social and economic developments in the region using a Bayesian network approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-create participatory rapid assessments of risks, opportunities and adaptation to biodiversity change by fishery management, communities and industry Organise a final stake-holder workshop for local communities/municipalities in case study regions to share results Produce a review of recent (10 years) Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) observations in Greenland in order to identify and categorise Greenlandic LEK observations and experienced impacts in relation to changing biodiversity and changing fisheries best placed to adopt those strategies

	Specific target	ECOTIP contribution	
EU Arctic Research Cluster	Provide policy-relevant information to respond to the impact of climate change on the Arctic's fragile marine ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in the EU Polar Cluster to boost the dissemination, uptake and utility of its results • Engage with sister projects FACE-IT and CHARTER and other projects (EU4OceanObs, OceanICU) to create synergies and enhance international cooperation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage in the use of common infrastructure to promote complementary actions • Provide policy advice through pro-active participation in the cluster to respond to the impact of climate change and to contribute to sustainable development

4 ECOTIP's Plan for the Dissemination of Results

4.1 What types of results will be made available through ECOTIP?

To investigate the drivers and ecosystem consequences of biodiversity change, ECOTIP has developed a comprehensive approach that will combine:

- maps of stressors in the Arctic ocean, both using global climate models, existing data series and new sampling - WP1
- data series on the abundance of organisms related to climatic and non-climatic stressors, spanning in time from recent millennia to present day, and covering different geographic areas and seasons – WP2
- experimental studies on organism's tolerance and adaptability, and process studies on the pelagic and benthic systems – WP1 and WP2
- trait-based models synthesising the ecosystem consequences of the biodiversity change, and predicting the future ecosystems – WP3
- statistical models predicting the future fish distributions – WP2
- Bayesian network to assess ecosystem vulnerability and to facilitate integration of local environmental knowledge with other field and model results – WP3, WP4 and WP5
- stakeholder workshops, interviews, case studies and data collection to collect baseline information on fleet structure and governance methods, and to explore changes, impacts and adaptation options with fishery stakeholders and indigenous communities – WP4 and WP5

ECOTIP is a multidisciplinary project which collects and generates new information spanning a number of disciplines, from physical oceanography to socio-economics. In Table 2 below we summarise the types or sources of data and model results which ECOTIP will generate and disseminate throughout the project lifetime. The majority of information will be widely disseminated and available for further exploitation by both scientific and non-scientific users, many of which we directly engage during the project to consult on their specific needs.

Current status of data and information collected in the project can be found in the next iterations of the Data Management Plan (<https://zenodo.org/record/5913413>).

Data

Table 2: Summary of data types and sources with examples of parameter groups.

Domain	Data/model	Type/source	Parameter groups	Dissemination level
socio-economics	raw data	personal interviews	<i>Fishermen and industry representatives</i>	non-open
	raw data & models	economic analysis	fishery fleets; governance models	open
	raw data	local ecological knowledge (LEK)	fish; other biological parameters	open
	video	media interviews	ECOTIP scientists	open
physical oceanography	raw data	seawater samples	water column temperature and salinity	open
	synthesis product	climate and stressor scenarios	water column temperature and salinity	open
biogeochemistry	raw data	seawater samples	dissolved gases; nutrients; carbonate system; suspended particulate material	open
	raw data	sediment traps	fluxes	open
	synthesis product	climate and stressor scenarios	oxygen, pH	open
biology	raw data	laboratory experiments	zooplankton; rate measurements (including production, excretion and grazing); fatty acids	open
	raw data	net tows	zooplankton	open
	raw data	acoustic surveys	fish	open
	synthesis product	remote sensing merged with in situ	pigments; phytoplankton and microphytobenthos	open
	raw data	seawater samples	pigments; bacteria and viruses; rate measurements (including production, excretion and grazing)	open
	raw data	omics, proteomics	other biological measurements	open
	raw data	eDNA	other organic chemical measurements	open
	raw data	chemical analysis	biota composition	open
	model	statistical model outputs	fish	open
model	Matlab routines of trait-based models	phytoplankton and microphytobenthos; zooplankton	open	
paleo oceanography	raw data	sediment cores	rock and sediment physical and chemical properties; rock and sediment biota; other organic chemical measurements	open

Scientific Knowledge

ECOTIP results will contribute significantly to a number of knowledge gaps identified by global assessments on the state of climate (e.g. IPCC) and biodiversity (e.g. IPBES). On a regional level, ECOTIP results will also address gaps in scientific knowledge and capacity reported by expert working groups of the Arctic Council, and ICES among others. Table 1 provides an extensive list of groups and organisations which ECOTIP will engage with to maximise dissemination as well as exploitation of specific new scientific knowledge.

The primary means of disseminating this new scientific knowledge will be through scientific publications. In order to maximise their potential for exploitation ECOTIP will also directly engage with relevant working groups, which several of ECOTIP consortium members are already active members of.

Storyline Groups: ECOTIP has established a number of dedicated task teams, spanning across two or more WPs, with the aim to among other things improve the focus of the research to maximise the exploitation of ECOTIP's new knowledge related to several so-called "storylines". Based on key questions and gaps identified from reports and assessments as well as through stakeholder interactions, each task team is responsible for refining and executing a set of adequate communication, dissemination and exploitation measures. These storylines include topics related to capelin migration, invasive species, benthic-pelagic coupling or cycling of lipids in the ecosystem, among others.

Apart from significantly improving collaboration within the project by better identifying links between WPs and tasks, formation of storyline groups is proving effective in facilitating connection with targeted stakeholder groups to address specific knowledge gaps (Table 3), and clarifying media and public outreach relevance of key scientific outcomes of ECOTIP.

Policy recommendations

ECOTIP results will provide recommendations for enhancing and optimising biodiversity monitoring efforts to support global and regional policies. Current capacity of long-term observations of marine biodiversity is being analysed with respect to scientific and societal requirements, and providing recommendations for enhanced and optimised monitoring in line with the best practices and international standards. Particular focus will be on 1) the development of recommendations based on the outcomes of WP4 - with additional input and synthesis WP1-3, on fisheries adaptation options in Greenland, and 2) monitoring elements currently not included in observing programs, such as invasive species via eDNA and on the benthic communities which can act as temporal couplers in the seasonal systems and reflect long term trends in overlaying water column production. Detailed recommendations for optimised sampling in the case study region of Greenland are being consulted with local managers and observing system implementers who will evaluate their impact and feasibility through a dedicated workshop planned towards the end of the project.

Using information from Tasks 1.2, 2.2-3 and 3.3 ECOTIP has informed the ongoing process of setting requirements for sustained global ocean observations of relevant Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) coordinated by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Marine Biodiversity Observing Network (MBON). Relevant EOV/EBV requirements, related to plankton in particular, will be refined with special consideration of data and information needs identified by climate (IPCC) and biodiversity (IPBES) assessments.

To this end, a series of dedicated workshops has been planned: an initial workshop focused on discussing ECOTIP project results (October 2022) and a final large international workshop gathering input from the broad scientific community (October 2023). The latter workshop is being conducted in collaboration with the EU4OceanObs project, and further synergies are being sought with the OceanICU project. Through this process, ECOTIP will ensure that the relevant EOV requirements are better co-designed by the observing and modelling communities whose communication remains severely limited and inefficient.

Methods

As can be seen from Table 2, ECOTIP has been employing a combination of traditional and novel methodologies to address current gaps in scientific knowledge and/or resource management. We can distinguish between methods used for (i) collection of raw data and (ii) methods used to analyse data and/or generate model projections.

(ii) data collection and experimental methods

In order to map the multitude of stressors affecting the Arctic ocean ecosystem, ECOTIP uses:

- in situ observations from past and new hydrographic and biological surveys conducted both in the open ocean and in coastal waters, including inside fjords.
- remote sensing observations of key environmental abiotic and biotic factors obtained from public repositories such as ESA Climate Change Initiative

To enable examining empirical responses of biota to changes in anthropogenic stressors the project relies on a number of well-established field data collection methods such as water sampling, net tows, acoustic surveys, sediment traps and sediment cores, as well as the rapidly developing methodologies of omics, proteomics and eDNA.

High innovation potential is associated with generalising the use of eDNA in fisheries and ecosystem surveys, moving the science from research to application (e.g. through enabling detection of invasive species in Arctic waters). This process engages scientists and stakeholders from Greenland to work with ECOTIP to co-develop pragmatic recommendations, including cost and feasibility assessments, for expanding eDNA observations beyond research projects and integrating them as part of monitoring efforts.

The new methodology in ECOTIP also includes development of paleo-oceanography to investigate the changes in biota over the past millennia, such as the detection of zooplankton remains in sediment cores. This would allow comparisons of past and present drivers of species distributions, and give new insights on the effects of multiple stressors and the speed of the recovery in marine biota. This new methodology along with the results will be described in a scientific publication, and will be available in open access.

In addition, ECOTIP has been conducting laboratory experiments with tolerance of organisms to complement field and modelling work so that combined information can help resolve the complex question of how organisms with different trait composition respond to changing conditions.

(ii) analysis methods and tools

To provide new insights into the functioning of the Arctic ecosystem, the project relies on statistical analysis of the links between biota and climatic and non-climatic stressors from last millennia to present day (Tasks 1.2, 1.3 and 2.1) and dedicated process studies to gain understanding of the cascading effects of the changes in the primary producers to the food web transfer and biological pump (Task 2.2).

In order to increase our capacity to predict changes in ecosystem services under scenarios of climate and human pressures, ECOTIP uses a trait-based approach to modelling the ecosystem interactions. This methodology represents a disruptive innovation in ecosystem modelling. By developing new model concepts and applications ECOTIP will for example increase the potential for resolving greater detail of biological processes in existing ecosystem models, including Earth System Models which will be used in the 7th Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP7) and form the basis for IPCC AR7.

Assessing the socio-economic consequences of Arctic biodiversity change and addressing the mitigation and adaptation options is done by:

- using mixed-method case studies of recent adaptations to ecosystem change in the inshore and off-shore fisheries and the fishery management system in West Greenland.
- conducting a retrospective analysis of economic, social and cultural impacts and trade-offs of different regulatory options, including the relative support for small- vs large- scale fisheries or commercial fishing vs other use of resources (e.g., tourism).
- mapping and organising the fishing fleet in homogeneous sub-fleets, and analysing the impact that management systems and measures, social networks, local traditions, and changes in biological community compositions and stock abundance, have on the fleet
- modelling the development of fishing effort, assuming the fishing fleet to adapt to changes in constraining factors, and optimising fleet performance within given constraints
- exploring, in a co-design approach, how fishery stakeholders perceive risks and opportunities in relation to changes in biodiversity and fish stock distribution.
- collecting Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) of biodiversity change and their impacts on the fishery by reviewing the recent (10 years) LEK observations in West Greenland

In this domain ECOTIP will use an innovative approach to co-create with local stakeholders in Greenland an assessment tool (based on a probabilistic Bayesian network model) that both integrates traditional knowledge with scientific expertise, and provides scenario-exploration capability relevant for both scientific and societal needs. The work on the Bayesian networks is carried out in close collaboration with storyline groups of ECOTIP, ensuring the effort spans across all WPs and involves co-creation with both scientists and stakeholders (e.g. through a dedicated workshop and personal interviews carried out in Greenland in 2021). Based on the early project work where possibilities of Bayesian network development were scoped out for a number of scientific and policy issues, we have now focused on two most practical applications which will be

finalised and presented to stakeholders in the final stage of the project. The first one will showcase our ability to test scenarios of capelin migration in the Arctic waters in response to combinations of changes in environmental factors. The scenario-exploration tool will be presented at the Greenland Science Week in November 2023 (tbc). The second model will further develop our ability to predict changes in the biological carbon pump using a combination of state-of-the-art observations and coupled physical-biological model projections, with final results presented in early 2024.

4.2 Who are ECOTIPs “results” stakeholders and target groups?

Figure 1 below illustrates the various pathways which the project uses to reach its targets.

Figure 1: Pipeline from ECOTIP results and outputs to its targets (reproduced from the project proposal). The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are listed under Monitoring and Evaluation. Note that following revisions to the PEDR, some stakeholder groups were deemed no longer relevant. Please see Table 3 below for the most up to date description of the pipeline.

Furthermore, Table 3 (below) provides a more extensive list and plan of which preferred pathways/measures and channels are being used according to each target group.

Table 3. Target groups and the dissemination and exploitation strategies to reach them	
Target Category and Specific Targets	Dissemination and exploitation measures and channels per target group (with responsible partners italicised)
<p>Scientific community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Individual scientists · Early career scientists · Specific scientific groups including working groups of the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and Integrated Marine Biosphere Research (IMBeR) · Other specific EU Cluster and specific projects) – FACE-It & Charter · Life Projects Nature and Biodiversity · Earth Observation products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scientific articles /PhD thesis (<i>all partners</i>) ● Scientific conferences (<i>all partners</i>) ● Webinars (<i>all partners</i>) ● ECOTIP website www.ecotip-arctic.eu and associated online repositories (<i>GRIDA-website, IOPAN-central ECOTIP repository, Zenodo, DTU-Researchgate, all partners – to feed info</i>) ● Social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter hashtag) including leverage via Partner Institutions (<i>GRIDA-website, DTU, etc</i>) ● Meeting with other projects including through EU Polar Cluster (<i>GRIDA & DTU in lead</i>) ● Summer school and online trainings on both scientific and media/communications including use of existing structures including Polar Cluster and possibly others e.g. APECS (<i>WP5 including GRIDA & DTU with input from relevant partners</i>) ● Media including opportunities through “The Conversation” and other outlets (<i>GRIDA in lead to coordinate with input from all partners</i>)
<p>Scientific Advisory Bodies</p> <p>Major scientific assessments and groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · IPCC · IPBES · GOOS Expert Panels · Working Groups of the Arctic Council · ICES Working group on Integrated Ecosystems Assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ECOTIP website and associated online repositories (<i>GRIDA-website, IOPAN-central ECOTIP repository, Zenodo</i>) ● Scientific articles /PhD thesis (<i>all partners</i>) ● Policy briefs on adaptation options / cookbook (<i>WP5 in collaboration with WP4</i>) ● Face to face meetings, briefings, and participation in meetings (<i>all partners</i>) ● Input of information directly to observers or governments involved in the scientific advisory bodies (<i>WP5 to keep an overview and alert to opportunities, with input and participation from all partners where relevant</i>) ● Possible Nomination of ECOTIP researchers to expert working groups in ICES, CAFF, AMAP and other working groups where opportunities arise (<i>WP5 to keep an overview and alert to opportunities, with input and participation from all partners where relevant</i>) ● Participation in peer review processes and open consultations as and when opportunities arise (<i>WP5 to keep an overview and alert to opportunities, with input and participation from all partners where relevant</i>)

<p>EU and other international bodies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU policy including Arctic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequent dialogue with EU Project Officer as a door opener to opportunities (<i>DTU in lead</i>) • Participation in peer review processes and open consultations (e.g. Arctic policy public consultation) (<i>WP5 in lead to identify opportunities for input with input and participation from all partners</i>) • Specific opportunities for policy briefings and input at EU events through the Polar Cluster and Results Booster process (<i>GRIDA & DTU to follow Polar Cluster process with input from all partners where relevant</i>) • Active participation of ECOTIP within the EU Polar Cluster • Nomination of ECOTIP researchers to the “EU Polar Expert Group” set up by EU PolarNet (<i>DTU & GRIDA to identify opportunities, all partners where relevant</i>) • Dedicated ECOTIP dissemination session at EU Parliament or other venue towards end of the project (<i>WP5 in lead</i>) • Use of EU Comms desk, Horizon Magazine and other media opportunities to reach EU policy makers (<i>GRIDA in lead to coordinate with input from all partners</i>)
<p>Indigenous and local communities in Greenland <i>(current list taken from ECOTIP Task Group on Stakeholder Interactions)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greenland Institute of Natural Resources /the Climate research Centre • SQAPK (travels or online) • Greenland Employers (also representing the three below) • Royal Greenland • Polar Seafood • Municipalities • Ministry of fisheries etc. • Ministry of environment etc. • Ministry of Industry etc. • Youth • ICC • WWF 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online and face to face meetings (<i>WP4 in lead</i>) • ECOTIP Stakeholder meetings (<i>WP4 in lead</i>) • Co-development approach and input from stakeholders during workshops(<i>WP4 in lead</i>) • Scientific presentations at townhalls/gymnasiums (<i>WP4 in lead</i>) • ECOTIP website (possible Greenlandic section based on expressed need) (<i>GRIDA</i>) • Social media especially Facebook and Instagram (<i>GRIDA & relevant partners and their press officers</i>) • Alerting local media to events, radio interviews etc. <i>through press releases and other means (WP4)</i> • Policy briefs on adaptation options and cookbook (<i>WP5 in collaboration with WP4</i>) • ECOTIP photo exhibit and preparatory work (<i>GRIDA in collaboration with WP4 and other partners</i>) • Other opportunities where available
<p>European Citizens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General interested citizens • < adults from 16+ (interested in “mainstream” newspapers and more complex topics) • Teachers and students in the 11/15 age group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of Press releases (<i>GRIDA & all partners and their press officers</i>) • Direct approach to media of interest (e.g. Arctic, European, Greenlandic) and working directly with journalists *including opportunities for embedding journalists in research (<i>GRIDA/DTU/all partners</i>) • Use of social media and leveraging partner institutions social media accounts (<i>GRIDA & all partners and their press officers</i>) • ECOTIP photo exhibit and collaboration with natural history museums or other *specific age group tbd (<i>GRIDA in lead</i>) • <i>Interaction with high school teachers and incorporation of tipping points into Danish curricula (DTU in lead)</i> •

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Public lectures (<i>all partners</i>)
NGOs and Private Sector organisations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● See above list for Greenland-specific list 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Face to face briefings (<i>all partners</i>) ● Interactions during conferences and working group & ● Policy briefs & cookbooks (<i>WP5 in collaboration with WP4</i>)

4.3 What are ECOTIP’s dissemination channels and platforms?

- **Open access scientific journals**

The primary means of disseminating the results of ECOTIP among the scientific community is through publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals. These publications help ensure ECOTIP’s main goals which are (i) to evaluate the consequences of biodiversity change in the Arctic marine environment, (ii) to estimate any potential tipping elements in the ecosystem functions behind these services, or (iii) to understand their effects on human societies.

ECOTIP conforms with H2020 requirements to make all peer-reviewed scientific publications generated by ECOTIP available in open-access. This means, at the very least, that we will ensure that these publications can be read online, downloaded and printed.

In close collaboration with the data management team and according to the Grant Agreement, we ensure that:

1. a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a repository (online archive) for scientific publications, as soon as possible and at the latest upon publication.
2. open access to publications is provided through:
 - a. self-archiving (green open-access)
 - b. open access publishing (gold open-access)
3. open access — via the repository — is provided to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication

The Management Team, after consultation with the steering committee, ensures requisite resources are available for at least 30 publications in golden open access mode. Whenever possible, use of gold open access is being encouraged through one of many open access journals searchable at <https://doaj.org/> - an independent, community-curated online directory that indexes and provides access to high quality, open access, peer-reviewed journals. Where applicable, ECOTIP will benefit from the new Open Research Europe publication services recently made available for all H2020 grant beneficiaries. ECOTIP project partners are being encouraged to consider submitting research manuscripts and/or data articles using this free, open and transparent (open peer-review) research publishing model. More details can be found at: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

ECOTIP partners should be cautious of journals which may misuse the Open Access model by charging high fees without providing adequate editorial services and peer review.

For details and tips on how ECOTIP will meet the open access requirements, please see Section 5.3. Project partners are also encouraged to make use of relevant fact-sheets prepared by the OpenAIRE project: <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-h2020-factsheets>

- **Data platforms and online data-results-model repositories:**

In ECOTIP, we have taken several steps to optimise means of disseminating observational data and model results through adequate platforms and repositories. Below is a brief summary. The periodically updated Data Management Plan contains more detailed information.

ECOTIP will use a dedicated central data repository, hosted at IOPAN and mirrored at servers of selected partner institutions. This repository enables the project to disseminate its results in accordance with all the FAIR data principles of (i) findability (ii) availability (iii) interoperability and (iv) reproducibility.

For dissemination purposes, project partners have been given the option to disseminate their results via the central ECOTIP repository or via databases and datastreams previously established at and preferred by their institutions. A common metadata standard was adopted by the ECOTIP consortium and a metadata public repository was set up by IOPAN to facilitate dissemination and exploitation of project results according to FAIR principles (see the current version of the Data Management Plan for details). Consequently, information about all project data collection activities are being recorded and available to partners and stakeholders via the ECOTIP GeoNetwork facility: [ECOTIP Geonetwork \(iopan.pl\)](https://www.iopan.pl/geonetwork).

Data will be initially available only within the project consortium. According to the ORDP, the data will be made publicly available on an agreed timeline unless subject to any concerns related to privacy, intellectual property rights or jeopardising the project's main objectives. Each dataset or product released will have an assigned DOI number. This service is being offered both by the ECOTIP central repository, and optionally also by Zenodo's ECOTIP community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/ecotip-arctic/>).

Depending on the type of data collected or products generated, results might be deposited into more field-specific databases, for example for molecular or socio-economic data.

New model code developed in ECOTIP is being freely and openly available to the public by depositing it on a version control GitHub public repository. All code will be published on GitHub during the duration of the project, and connected to the ECOTIP Zenodo community. As in the case of data and scientific publications, EU funding must be acknowledged.

- **Webinars and other online platforms**

ECOTIP is making use of online platforms and has used webinars to disseminate the results of the project. Particularly in the later stages of the project, when a good volume of results is available. ECOTIP will make use of its existing channels and networks, including the Polar Cluster, European Polar Board and other networks, to advertise such events and ensure a high level of relevant participation.

- **ECOTIP website**

The ECOTIP website (ecotip-arctic.eu) serves as a gateway for information about the project and its results. It serves both as a communication and dissemination platform. All major results of the project, including published scientific articles, are highlighted under the “Resources” and specifically within the section “Publications and Results”. New, relevant results are highlighted through blog articles with links to Zenodo. To monitor the scientific outputs and ensure timely dissemination, the website will automatically harvest bibliographic metadata from the ECOTIP Community on Zenodo. In addition, all deliverables of the project that are labelled as “public” will be hosted on the project website through Zenodo.

- **Press releases and social media**

ECOTIP has a media and social media strategy which is elaborated in detail in the Communications plan (see Annex of that plan). Press releases are being developed, (in collaboration with partner institutions press officers where relevant) for journal articles and other results which are likely to generate interest by other scientists and the broader public. For any results that are likely to generate major interest in the media, DTU/GRIDA must be informed and is required to liaise and inform the EU Commission well in advance. In addition, targeted social media messages are being developed on a case by case basis, and rolled out through partner institutions.

- **ECOTIP Policy briefs and publications**

For non-scientific audiences, ECOTIP will produce a “cookbook” (D5.7) which in practise will comprise at least two policy brief(s) related to 1) the socio-economic work and development of possible adaptation options and recommendations for fisheries stakeholders in Greenland, and 2) eDNA monitoring and management. The policy briefs will digest the most important scientific findings in language relevant for policy makers. additional policy briefs may be considered for good opportunities throughout the project, for example at important EU or national or regional events. One example is the policy brief developed for the mid-term policy meeting jointly with FACE-IT and CHARTER. In developing such publications, ECOTIP will seek the inclusion and partnership with important stakeholders or target groups themselves to ensure there is a strong ownership of the results and the process.

- **Targeted face to face briefings**

Face to face meetings are an important dissemination tool and ECOTIP has been using these where necessary and where possible considering significant restrictions due to COVID-19. Face to face interactions have proven particularly efficient and impactful during the second period of the project, and the same is anticipated for the final months of the project.

- **Nomination of experts to scientific / policy assessment processes, working groups etc.**

As elaborated under Table 3, ECOTIP will track important assessment and policy processes and identify possible opportunities for the nomination of ECOTIP scientists to form part of such processes. Particular focus has been placed on strengthening the project’s representations in the

ICES WGIEAGS because of the strong and unique expertise as well as the heavy field work carried out by ECOTIP in the Greenland Sea Ecoregion.

- **Events:**

Events, whether online or in person, are key for ECOTIP to disseminate its results and promote exploitation. A calendar is kept regularly up to date for the coming year ahead in order to ensure sufficient advance preparation ahead of each event, and for tracking and KPI purposes. It is the responsibility of partners to keep track of events attended, what was presented and approximate audience numbers.

The type of events that ECOTIP engages in is broad and depends on the target audiences, and includes:

- Scientific conferences
- Scientific and advisory group meetings
- EU Polar Cluster and related meetings
- Stakeholder meetings in Greenland
- Policy relevant events

- **Summer schools & training workshops**

ECOTIP has developed an online communications training (ECTS credit) workshop for early career scientists which was rolled out in 2021 and can be replicated in future years based on needs. This training was further built on the ECOTIP summer school “Ecological Tipping Points In The Arctic And How To Communicate Them.”

Twelve early-career researchers participated in the ECOTIP summer school, held at Husö Biological Station on the Åland Islands, Finland from June 6th – 17th 2022. During an intense two weeks, they received scientific lectures and practical training focusing on the rapid environmental, ecological and social changes happening in the Arctic – and how to communicate them - from world-class experts. The students also earned course credits, built their professional networks and showcased their research. More information on the Course can be found on the project website [here](#).

4.4 Strategy for the exploitation of ECOTIP results

Apart from communication through peer-reviewed literature and scientific conference presentations, ECOTIP will liaise with a number of international research projects and programs such as IMBeR, IOCCP and US OCB to contribute to their scientific agendas and implementation plans. Furthermore, we will liaise with, build on or contribute to the work of several international expert working groups whose terms of reference are compatible with the objectives of ECOTIP. These include the IOC-UNESCO WG on Integrated Ocean Carbon Research particularly with respect to the impact of plankton diversity changes on ocean carbon sequestration, the Integrated Marine Biosphere Research (IMBeR) Human Dimensions Working Group, or the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) Working Group 149: “Changing Ocean Biological Systems (COBS): How will biota respond to a changing ocean?” .

ECOTIP has also established close interaction with similar-minded Horizon 2020 projects, FACE-IT and CHARTER in particular, to optimise the synergies among projects and also increase the efficiency of results exploitation. The 2021 annual meetings of ECOTIP and CHARTER forged a report outlining the goal to collaborate, and there was subsequent collaboration with both FACE-IT and CHARTER projects for a mid-term policy brief and event, as well as joint factsheets showcasing final results of the projects.

Close collaboration has also been established between ECOTIP and the EU4OceanObs project (<https://www.mercator-ocean.eu/en/eu4oceanobs/>) particularly around bridging the gap between what the modelling community needs and what the observing and data management communities can provide when it comes to advancing our capacity to understand and predict changes in Arctic biodiversity and associated ecosystem services. Further potential synergies are continuously sought out, most recently with the OceanICU project (<https://ocean-icu.eu/>).

4.4.1 Exploitation of data

ECOTIP will produce and disseminate new data according to FAIR principles. We will maximise the exploitation potential of new data by encouraging submission to public databases and data integrators which require use of common vocabularies and standards for metadata and data, respectively. . The establishment and common use of the dedicated GeoNetwork facility for all ECOTIP metadata records enables ECOTIP stakeholders but also any interested users to navigate through all ECOTIP data and obtain machine-readable access and exploit ECOTIP project results from a single entry point, pending their publication.

In addition, we take measures to actively encourage certain groups of users and stakeholders to exploit project results. This has been done through pointing towards adequate data during expert working group meetings, technical workshops as well as scientific conferences, etc.

4.4.2 Exploitation of new knowledge

ECOTIP will facilitate optimal exploitation of project results to address gaps in knowledge related to the Arctic climate, marine biodiversity change, its drivers and consequences, as identified by IPCC, IPBES and relevant international expert working groups providing scientific assessments and policy advice.

A newly established ICES WG on Integrated Ecosystem Assessment in the Greenland Sea has in particular benefited from project results (Tasks 2.1-3, 3.3), feeding into annual ICES ecosystem overview advice. Direct and early communication with the WG, through joint membership in both ECOTIP and the ICES WG of one of consortium partners, has maximised the potential of ECOTIP to generate data and knowledge of exploitable value by the ICES WG. Early work has led to ECOTIP identifying existing data sources within the Greenland Sea ecoregion which the ICES WG did not consider in their initial stock-taking. Moreover, discussions with ICES WG members helped inform the sampling program and design for the ECOTIP cruise in East Greenland planned for August 2022.

To address fundamental biological processes which remain unquantified and as such are a key knowledge gap identified by IPCC, ECOTIP will promote the uptake of new mechanistic

understanding and a trait-based approach (Tasks 2.2-3, 3.1-2) in existing Earth System Models used to inform regional and global climate assessment. To this end, new model code developed during the project's lifetime (e.g. using GitHub's private repositories; web-based hosting service for version control using Git) is being opened to the public to foster further exploitation and innovation among the ecosystem and climate modelling communities.

ECOTIP plans to participate actively via GRID-Arendal in the working groups of the Arctic Council was cut short by the decision, at least formally, of all Arctic Council states apart from Russia to halt Arctic Council work while under the Russian Chairmanship. Nonetheless, ECOTIP has kept in dialogue with the CAFF Secretariat and sought synergies particularly with the CBMP. . ECOTIP is a member of the EU Polar Cluster and contributes to its activities including generating policy advice. ECOTIP has representation in each of the working groups of the EU Polar Cluster.

Table 1 in Section 3 provides a summary of other examples of new knowledge and targets for its exploitation as currently initiated and anticipated by ECOTIP.

In addition, it should be noted that after the official end of the project, the current project website will be transformed into the ECOTIP Research Findings website providing access to the research results of the project to support future research and investment, scientific assessments as well as marine management decisions and policies. The domain name of the project website will be assigned to DTU. The website and ECOTIP central data repository at IOPAN will archive all documentation related to the project, including publications, and will be accessible for 5 years after the end of the project.

5 Main Tasks and Responsibilities in Dissemination and Exploitations

5.1 Partner' Responsibilities & timeline

A summary of the responsibilities and involvement of each partner with regards to dissemination and exploitation is outlined under Table 3. Each partner also has the responsibility of tracking its own activities and where relevant its impact, through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which are outlined in this document under Monitoring and Evaluation. A few useful guides have been developed to aid partners in their obligations:

- **An open access peer-reviewed publication checklist (See Annex)** has been developed for the process required with open access journal articles, which all partners should follow.
- **A summary sheet for partners on ECOTIP Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation & Data Management** has been prepared (attached as Annex to this Plan) which includes useful reminders, a quick guide to the various obligations and good practice for all partners to follow. This includes guidance on the below:

5.2 Acknowledgement of EU funding and disclaimer

In disseminating the project results the beneficiaries will acknowledge the research funding according to the Art. 29.4, 29.5 and or Art. 38.1.2. of the grant agreement.

Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869383 (ECOTIP)".

NB! When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. ECOTIP partners may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency.

NB! Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

5.3 Open Access requirements

ECOTIP complies with all EU requirements regarding provision of open access to project results. This includes mandatory open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications generated by the project, following three steps as described above in the section on "scientific journals".

Majority of ECOTIP publications will be disseminated in green open access mode. If needed, WP5 will assist each author in self-archiving preprints in a freely accessible institutional or specialist online repository, or on a website. To ensure maximum flexibility for authors and maximum impact for the project, authors will be able to choose between self-archiving preprints in the ECOTIP central

repository (see section above), or at one of the open access reprint servers such as zenodo.org, arxiv.org, or more specifically for biological results: biorxiv.org. A dedicated Zenodo community has been set up for the ECOTIP project (<https://zenodo.org/communities/ecotip-arctic/>). All the available repositories have the capacity to assign DOIs. It is important that each deposited publication must be accompanied bibliographic metadata placed also in the repository including the following: (i) terms ["European Union (EU)" & "Horizon 2020"], (ii) name of action, acronym and grant number - *see suggested formula text in section above*, (iii) publication date, the length of the embargo period (if applicable) and a persistent identifier.

As recommended by the Commission, ECOTIP partners are encouraged to retain their copyright and grant adequate licences to publishers, e.g. through one of Creative Commons licences. Where possible, contributors should also be uniquely identifiable, and data uniquely attributable, through identifiers which are persistent, non-proprietary, open and interoperable (e.g. through leveraging existing sustainable initiatives such as ORCID for contributor identifiers and DataCite for data identifiers).

Providing open access to peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals is the responsibility of all project partners who are encouraged to use the ECOTIP open access publication checklist available in the Appendix. While the dominant type of scientific publication is the journal article, ECOTIP scientists are also strongly encouraged to provide open access to other types of scientific publications including:

- monographs
- books
- conference proceedings
- grey literature (informally published written material not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g. reports).

ECOTIP also strives to maximise open access to project's data which is needed to evaluate or reproduce the results from ECOTIP scientific publications. Our voluntary commitment to the Open Research Data Pilot is described briefly below, and in greater detail in the Data Management Plan.

5.4 Open Research Data Pilot

ECOTIP participates in the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) which enables open access and reuse of research data generated by ECOTIP as a Horizon 2020 project. This means that ECOTIP will meet the following conditions:

- develop (and keep up-to-date) a Data Management Plan (DMP).
- deposit data in a research data repository.
- ensure third parties can freely access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate data.
- provide related information and identify (or provide) the tools needed to use the raw data to validate our research.

These conditions set by the ORDP will apply to:

- the data (and metadata) needed to validate results in scientific publications.
- other curated and/or raw data (and metadata) which we specify in the DMP.

The accompanying deliverable Initial Data Management Plan provides details on how ECOTIP will manage and preserve data according to these ORDP requirements, while also considering the need to balance openness with protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, and security.

6 Risks and barriers to exploitation and their mitigation

The following risks and possible barriers have been identified, and strategies for their mitigation in the project are elaborated below.

Table 5	
Risk or barrier	Mitigation strategy
Project delays and mismatch between timing of outputs and deliverables across different work packages leading to further delays and less effective approach	ECOTIP has established several layers of communication to ensure that issues are spotted in a timely manner. These include the meetings of the steering committee, regular work package meetings, a number of “task groups” dedicated to special cross-work package topics, and storyline groups. These ensure there is sufficient communication across work packages and partners. Communications are facilitated through the use of a dedicated platform, SLACK.
Mismatch of timelines between assessments and policy processes and ECOTIP results	ECOTIP is identifying in advance opportunities to engage in policy processes to ensure effective planning of resources. In addition, ECOTIP will ensure research results will be available on time before committing to engage in specific policy processes.
A lack of Stakeholder interest, engagement and or understanding for the Bayesian networks work	ECOTIP is undertaking regular stakeholder meetings including pre-meeting online discussions in order to introduce the topic, goals etc. This is supported by effective communication from WP5 to ensure there is a good understanding of the process and the desired outcomes and benefit to the stakeholders.
COVID-19 and possible other side effects including restricted travel	ECOTIP has monitored this situation very closely and taken appropriate mitigation measures. These included holding meetings online as far as possible, including with stakeholders; working with existing partners and institutions on the ground, and planning for these risks and being realistic about what can be achieved.

7 Monitoring and Evaluation

7.1 ECOTIP's Key Performance Indicators

ECOTIP's Key Performance Indicators are in-line/complementary to the indicators used for the periodic reporting to the EU.

Key Performance Indicator	Specific Indicator	Roles / Responsibilities
KPI 1: Online communications reach, (social) media footprint	Number of website unique visitors/ unique visits/pageviews over a given time period	WP5 with input from partners
	Number of downloads of information products, estimated readership	WP5 with input from partners
	Audience statistics for both print and online media reach (on other platforms)	WP5 with input from partners
KPI 2: Face-to-face meetings	Number of people attending events including presentations, public lectures, etc.	All partners responsible for gathering estimates of number of people attending events (in person or online) – will be collated by WP5
	User feedback on quality and design of products targeted at different audiences.	All partners responsible for keeping testimonials (e.g. written emails or other) expressing user feedback – will be collated by WP5
KPI 3: Policy impact	Number of management/policy-relevant recommendations developed by the project, as would appear in policy briefings or other documents.	All partners responsible for monitoring where relevant, WP5 will collate
KPI 4: Science impact	Number of publications, number of citations, number of reads and downloads from preprint repositories (e.g. journal websites, ResearchGate). Citations will also be tracked on Google Scholar.	All partners responsible for monitoring where relevant their publications, WP5 will collate
KPI 5: Collaboration and synergies	Number of partners engaged in activities led by or co-organized by ECOTIP	All partners, WP5 will collate
	Number of cluster activities sponsored/co-organized	All partners, WP5 will collate

KPI 6: Local and indigenous societies	Number of outputs from stakeholders with regards to expert opinion in Bayesian model development	All partners, WP5 will collate
	Number of users of assessment tools	All partners especially WP4 , WP 5 will collate
	Number of people engaged from relevant Indigenous communities/local communities in the project	All partners but especially WP4 – WP5 will collate

8 Annex

8.1 Open Access Publication (OA) Checklist for ECOTIP partners

During writing/submission of a manuscript

- Check in the DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) if the journal of your choice allows Open Access publishing/if there is an OA-deal.
- Contact DTU ahead of the planned submission to verify eligibility for publication cost reimbursement, and to agree whether the publication will follow the gold or green open access track. If using a subscription-based journal, check on [SHERPA/RoMEO](#) which article version (e.g. pre-print or post-print) is free to be made publicly available at which time (green OA).
- Prior to submission, ensure that all contributors have a persistent identifier associated with their names, e.g. [ORCID](#).

At submission

- Indicate during submission that you wish to publish OA.
- Provide ORCID identifiers for each contributor.
- Acknowledge project funding by including the following text into the manuscript: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869383”.

After publication:

- In one of the agreed repositories deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of either:
 - the published version of the article (gold OA), or
 - the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, pre-print or a post-print (green OA).
- Contact IOPAN and confirm the publication DOI along with other bibliographic metadata.
- When using Green OA, verify that open access to a version of the publication is provided no later than 6 months after publication (12 months for Social Sciences and Humanities)

8.2 ECOTIP Miniguide for Communication and Dissemination of Project Results

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 869383

Mini Guide on Communications and Dissemination for ECOTIP researchers

This is a very quick guide on communicating/disseminating your work in ECOTIP. It is based on the Communication, Dissemination and Data Management Strategies.

⇒ You can access these strategies in the NextCloud, under “Deliverables” – D5.1-5.3.

How to access Nextcloud

⇒ Through this link <http://ecotip.iopan.pl/nxc/index.php/login>

⇒ Your username and password has been provided to you by Marcin and Artur. If you have any problems, message Marcin by Slack or email wichor@iopan.pl

Accessing logos, and templates for powerpoint presentations

Please use the ECOTIP logo where possible and the ppt template for your ECOTIP presentations. *This is important as the templates include the EU logo and acknowledgement of funding, which is a requirement to include for all public presentations of ECOTIP.*

⇒ You can access the EU logo, ECOTIP logos and word and powerpoint templates in NextCloud, in the folder “Logos_Templates”

Do you have anything newsworthy to share?

The communication team (WP5) wants to hear if you have been to any interesting event, including conferences, meetings, or other events. It is nice for us to share news and keep the website and Facebook page updated with new content, and it shows that the project is active.

⇒ get in touch with Björn through slack or email (bjorn.alfthan@grida.no) and we can work with you to share the news.

⇒ Remember to take photos if it was a live event!

What about social media?

ECOTIP is active primarily on Facebook and Instagram. We do not have an active Twitter account but encourage the use of hashtags.

⇒ If you want to post directly to the Facebook page, you can do so:

<https://www.facebook.com/EcoTipArctic/> The post will be reviewed by Bjorn before it is published.

Please contact Sabrina Heerema (sabrina.heerema@grida.no) or through Slack if you want to post anything on our Facebook or Instagram accounts

⇒ Facebook page is <https://www.facebook.com/EcoTipArctic/>

⇒ Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/ecotiparctic/>

⇒ Twitter hashtag #EcoTipArctic

Are you in the process of publishing a paper? / do you want help with a press release?

Contact us at least 6 weeks in advance of expected publication, so that we can help prepare a press release and plan for launch.

⇒ Get in touch with Artur (a.palacz@ioccp.org) or Björn through Slack or email.

Acknowledging ECOTIP and the funder (H2020) in any published work

Any published work, including any conference presentations, which is in full or part supported by the ECOTIP project is obliged to:

⇒ Display the EU emblem AND include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869383 (ECOTIP)”.

⇒ The easiest way to do this is to include the EU logo which already has the acknowledgement written underneath it. (see Nextcloud : “Logos_Templates”)

See below for acknowledgements in journals.

Checklist for Open-Access Publishing

During writing/submission of a manuscript

⇒ Check in the DOAJ ([Directory of Open Access Journals](#)) if the journal of your choice allows Open Access (OA) publishing/if there is an OA-deal.

⇒ Contact Sigrún (sjo@aqua.dtu.dk) ahead of the planned submission to verify eligibility for publication cost reimbursement, and to agree whether the publication will follow the gold or green open access track. If using a subscription-based journal, check on [SHERPA/RoMEO](#) which article version (e.g. pre-print or post-print) is free to be made publicly available at which time (green OA).

Prior to submission

⇒ Ensure that all contributors have a persistent identifier associated with their names, e.g. [ORCID](#).

At submission

⇒ Indicate during submission that you wish to publish OA.

⇒ Provide ORCID identifiers for each contributor.

⇒ Acknowledge project funding by including the following text into the manuscript: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869383”.

After publication:

⇒ In ZENODO (see details below), deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of either:

- the published version of the article (gold OA), or
- the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, pre-print or a postprint (green OA).

⇒ Contact Artur at IOPAN and confirm the publication DOI along with other bibliographic metadata.

⇒ When using Green OA, verify that open access to a version of the publication is provided no later than 6 months after publication (12 months for Social Sciences and Humanities)

ZENODO: guidance on publishing results and material on this platform

ECOTIP is using ZENODO to share all open-access publications and other results (e.g. presentations, reports, videos). All partners are required to upload their open-access results to this platform. A separate repository for data and metadata sharing is set up for ECOTIP at IOPAN (contact Marcin).

A dedicated ECOTIP community has been created on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/ecotip-arctic/?page=1&size=20> which is also now linked to the ECOTIP website results page: <https://ecotip-arctic.eu/results/>

- ⇒ Navigate to: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=ecotip-Arctic>
- ⇒ You will need to create a new account if you have not already done so.
- ⇒ See further instructions on the last page of this document.
- ⇒ Any problems, please contact Artur or Björn

Keeping track of the impact of my work for monitoring and evaluation

We have a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which each partner will need to keep track of.

Please remember to keep track of:

- ⇒ what work can be considered part of ECOTIP work and can be published under the ECOTIP (*see acknowledging ECOTIP above*)
- ⇒ number of attendees/audience size at an ECOTIP events (virtual or face to face)
- ⇒ testimonials – this is expressed feedback on the satisfaction of a product or service
- ⇒ policy impact of your work: has it resulted in a mention in a policy document
- ⇒ # ECOTIP publications, number of citations, number of downloads etc.